

Units of measure and styles vary from country to country. To improve communication and to speed the editorial process, the editors of the *International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN)* request that contributors use the following style guidelines:

- Use the metric system in all papers. Avoid national units of measure (such as cavans, rai, etc.).

- Express all yields in tons per hectare (t/ha) or, with small-scale studies, in grams per pot (g/pot) or grams per row (g/row).

- Define in footnotes or legends any abbreviations or symbols used in a figure or table.

- Place the name or denotation of compounds or chemicals near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha; not 60 kg/ha N.

- The US dollar is the standard monetary unit for the IRRI. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.

- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg/ha.

- Express time, money, and measurement in numbers, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 years; 3 kg/ha at 2-week intervals; 7%; 4 hours.

- When possible, round off numbers to one or two decimal points. For example, 5.2 t/ha, not 5.232.

- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing some numbers 10 or higher and some numbers lower than 10. For example: six parts; seven tractors; four varieties. But There were 4 plots in India, 8 plots in Thailand, and 12 plots in Indonesia.

- Write out all numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were added to each cage; Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer use.

- Type all contributions double-spaced.

Genetic evaluation and utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

Inheritance of gamma ray-induced multipistillate mutant in rice

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F₁ seed from the cross NSJ 200/Badshah Pasand at 12% moisture content were irradiated with 25 Kr gamma rays from a 60 Co source. In M₂, four 100% male-sterile and multipistillate plants were observed. Each floret consisted of gynoecium with four ovaries and eight styles. All ovaries were fused together, leaving four conspicuous grooves. However, the number of stamens—six—was normal. Both lemma and palea were narrow and semilunar in shape and could not completely cover the androecium and gynoecium. These multipistillate plants produced a few seed that germinated by outcrossing, but the seedlings were poor. A single seed was produced by each floret, indicating that only one pistil was fertile.

In M₃, 30 plant progeny, each consisting of 50 plants, were grown. Six plant progeny segregated into normal and male-sterile multipistillate plants (see table). Of the 300 plants, 16 were male-sterile and multipistillate. Statistical analysis showed that this character is probably governed by duplicate genes ($X^2 = 0.4301$, $P > 0.50$ for 15: 1 ratio). The mutation can be explained

Segregation of six rice plant progeny into male sterile multipistillate plants.^a

Line	Mutants	Normal plants	Total
2	1	49	50
7	3	41	50
9	1	49	50
11	2	48	50
24	5	45	50
28	4	46	50
Total	16	284	300

^a X^2 (15:1) = 0.4301, $P > 0.50$

genetically as follows: Let G₁ and G₂ be duplicate genes, any of which produces normal pistils. When both are homozygous recessive, they produce male-sterile multipistillate plants. The genotype of parents in this case might be G₁G₁G₂G₂ and g₁g₁G₂G₂. The mutation took place at the G₂ locus, involving one of the two alleles.

Diffusion of genetic materials among Asian rice breeding programs

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Although researchers have studied the spread of the improved rice varieties onto farmers' fields, little is known about their diffusion as parent varieties into breeding programs. Through analysis of breeding records and in-depth interviews with the breeders who made the crosses, IRRI attempted to trace the diffusion of genetic materials used as parents over a 10-year period, from the mid-1960's through the mid-1970's, at 14 agricultural experiment stations and universities in 7 Asian nations. The breeders represented 7 centers in India, 2 in Korea, and 1 center each in Bangladesh, Indonesia, the Philippines, Sri Lanka, and Thailand. The research project was partially funded by The Rockefeller Foundation.

Three hundred and fifty-five crosses, involving 819 parents, were randomly selected from the breeding records for 3 time periods: 1965–67, 1970–71 and 1974–75. The percentages of semidwarf, intermediate-statured, tall, and deep-water or floating rices used during each period were calculated on a cross basis—the percentage of total crosses in which a variety of each plant type was used as a donor parent—and on an individual-parent basis—the percentage of different types of rice in the total gene pool.

Sixty-one percent of the 1965–67